

MODELING OF THERMAL OXIDATION AND DAMAGE IN FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Lightweight fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites are increasingly used in advanced high-temperature structures, such as high-performance propulsion systems, high-speed aircraft structures and advanced microelectronics. In many of these load-bearing systems, temperature could reach 427°C (800°F) for a sustained period of time. At such a high temperature, the composite behaves as a thermodynamically open system, allowing oxygen to diffuse through and react with it. Mechanical loads and environmental attacks may cause microstructural change and property degradation. In this paper, an analytical modeling of thermal oxidative degradation of the fiber composite is attempted. The study is based on the recently developed coupled constitutive theory with reactions and damage. The well-known homogenization method is used to address the issues at both micro- and macro-scales. With the aid of high-temperature experiments on carbon/polyimide composites, oxidation mechanisms and roles of the fiber-matrix interface are identified and determined. The micromechanics approach accounts for complex interactions among neighboring fibers and enables us to investigate the effects of the oxidized surface layer and active oxidation zone along the fiber-matrix interface on local stress concentrations. The numerical results provide further understanding of high-temperature composite oxidation and elucidate intricacy of various parameters to materials tailoring and microstructural optimization for the composite system.

KEYWORDS: multi-scale modeling, interface, environmental concerns, mechanical & physical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in high-temperature polymer-matrix composites have led to significant interests in their applications to advanced engineering systems, such as high-performance propulsion systems, high-speed aircraft structures and advanced microelectronics. The temperature in many load-bearing polymer-matrix composites could reach 427°C/800°F for a sustained period of time. Long-term thermal oxidation is expected to cause severe weight loss and dimensional instability, and affects mechanical creep and chemical and physical aging. These complicated thermomechanical and physicochemical processes may occur simultaneously in both fiber and matrix phases as well as at the interface. The composite used in these systems must be capable of withstanding the severe environment but still maintaining their load-bearing structural integrity. Hence, understanding the thermal oxidative stability is of vital importance for long-term durability of polymer-matrix composites in high-temperature applications.

A significant amount of work has been conducted on polyimide neat resins and their carbon fiber composites [1-10]. The inherent difficulties of the thermal oxidative problem involve the complex microstructural change, the non-uniform skin-core structure, and the complex role of the fiber-matrix interface.

Early predictive modeling [11] of oxidation mechanisms and associated mechanical property degradation has been attempted for predicting the change in strength and modulus of wood during fire, and later used for fiber composites. The reductions in strength and modulus are found to depend solely on the mass loss through empirical relationships. McManus et al. [12] propose a mechanism-based model to address long-term degradation in polymer-matrix composites. The model has only limited success as it does not account for the coupling effects.

In this paper, a thermodynamic formulation has been made to model high-temperature oxidation of carbon/polyimide composites, based on the recently developed coupled constitutive theory with reactions and damage. A homogenization method is then used to relate the microscopic thermal

oxidative damage to macroscopic thermomechanical property degradation. Numerical results are presented on the cases of axial oxidation of a carbon/polyimide composite. The results are discussed in conjunction with experimental observations.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THERMAL OXIDATION OF CARBON/POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

Thermal oxidation experiments have been conducted in CEAC laboratories on carbon/polyimide composites and their individual constituents at elevated temperatures to determine their high-temperature oxidation behavior and associated microstructural changes [2-3]. Main features of the composite oxidation results reveal anisotropic reaction, damage in the skin-core structure, weight loss, and dimensional changes.

Fig. 1 Composite Oxidation

Fig.2 Side view of oxidation-induced damage in Avimid-N/IM6 after exposure at 650°F/343°C in air for 476 hours.

Fig.3 Weight loss per unit area during isothermal axial oxidation of Avimid-N/IM6 at 650°F/343°C.

Thermal oxidation in the composite is found to be directionally dependent (Fig.1). It also creates a skin-core structure since oxygen diffusion and oxidation reaction proceed inwards from the exposed surface. Oxidation-induced damage in Avimid-N/IM6 after exposure at 650°F/343°C in air is shown in Fig.2. Comparison of the weight loss per unit area with that determined by rule of mixture during isothermal axial oxidation of Avimid-N/IM6 at 650°F/343°C is shown in Fig.3. The composite weight loss calculated by the rule of mixture is found significantly less than the measured data. The difference has been attributed to the fiber-matrix interface, which has generally a higher free energy state with favorable oxygen diffusion paths for the composite oxidation.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS FOR A MULTICOMPONENT OPEN SYSTEM WITH REACTIONS AND DAMAGE

Thermodynamic principles have commonly been used to formulate material constitutive theories without involving chemical reactions. For example, Christensen has shown in [13] a thermodynamic derivation of coupled thermoviscoelastic constitutive equations without reactions and damage using the free energy approach. Abdel-Tawab and Weitsman [14] have also developed a thermodynamic framework for modeling coupled damage and viscoelastic creep with the aid of the superposition principle to effective stress and strain tensors. Damage evolution is described by employing the concept of damage surfaces in the strain space. In this paper, a thermodynamic approach, based on the recently developed coupled constitutive theory with reactions and damage [15], is presented for a multicomponent open system in an oxidative environment.

Consider a multicomponent open system with multiple simultaneous reactions. The first principal on conservation of mass requires the concentration of the i -th component, $c^{(i)}$, satisfy the following:

$$\frac{Dc^{(i)}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_m^{(i)} - r^{(i)} \quad (1)$$

with

$$r^{(i)} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \sum_p v_p^{(i)} M^{(i)} \dot{\xi}_p \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_i v_p^{(i)} M^{(i)} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $D/Dt = (\partial/\partial t + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)$; $c^{(i)} = \rho^{(i)}/\rho$, $\rho^{(i)}$, the i th component density, ρ , the total mass density; $\mathbf{j}_m^{(i)}$, the mass flux; $r^{(i)}$, the consumption rate in reactions; $\dot{\xi}_p$, the reaction rate for the p th reaction; $v_p^{(i)}$, the stoichiometric coefficient of the i th component in the p th reaction equation (the negative sign “-” for reactants, and positive sign “+” for products); and $M^{(i)}$, the molar mass of the i th component.

Specifically, the oxygen consumption rate, $r^{(Ox)}$, may be determined from a proposed mechanistic scheme [16, 17] of polymer oxidation as

$$r^{(Ox)} = r_0 \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \beta c^{(Ox)})^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

where r_0 is the saturation level of oxygen consumption rate, and β is a parameter.

Through irreversible thermodynamics formulation, the resulting coupled constitutive equations with reactions and damage for finite deformation may be obtained from the polynomial expansion of the Gibbs free energy as a functional of the stress, temperature, and reaction history with the introduction of damage as an internal variable:

$$E_{ij} = L_{ij}(0) + \int_{-\infty}^t S_{ijkl}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{kl}(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\lambda + \int_{-\infty}^t \alpha_{ij}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial T(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\lambda - \sum_p \int_{-\infty}^t \gamma_{ij}^p(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_p(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\lambda \quad (5)$$

$$\rho_0 \hat{s} = M(0) + \int_{-\infty}^t \alpha_{ij}(t - \tau, 0; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \frac{1}{T_0} \int_{-\infty}^t C(t - \tau, 0; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial T(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \sum_p \int_{-\infty}^t \kappa^p(t - \tau, 0; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_p(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\rho_0}{\rho} A_p = N^p(0) - \int_{-\infty}^t \gamma_{ij}^p(t - \tau, 0; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^t \kappa^p(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial T(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\lambda - \sum_q \int_{-\infty}^t B^{pq}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_q(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\lambda \quad (7)$$

where Σ_{ij} is the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor; E_{ij} , Green strain tensor; \mathbf{D} , damage tensor; T , temperature; ξ_p , extent of the p th reaction; A_p , affinity of the p th reaction; $S_{ijkl}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D})$, $\alpha_{ij}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D})$, $C(t - \tau, 0; \mathbf{D})$, $\gamma_{ij}^p(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D})$, $\kappa^p(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D})$ and $B^{pq}(0, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D})$ are appropriate memory functions of thermomechanical and physicochemical properties (i.e., compliance, thermal expansion coefficients, reaction contraction coefficients, heat capacity, thermochemical coefficients, and reactance). The first terms L_{ij} , M and N^p on right-hand sides of Eqs.(5), (6) and (7) stand for the reference state, the second terms for mechanical contribution, the third terms for thermal contribution, and the fourth terms for physicochemical contribution.

The kinetic law of damage evolution may also be determined by the second principle [18]. In terms of the generalized energy release rate $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$, the damage rate $\dot{\mathbf{D}}$ may be derived from a potential of damage $F_D(\hat{\mathbf{Y}}; \mathbf{D})$ as

$$\dot{\mathbf{D}} = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}} F_D(\hat{\mathbf{Y}}; \mathbf{D}) \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ involves mechanical, thermal and physicochemical energy released by damage growth as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{Y}} = & \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} L_{ij}(t - \tau; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} M(t - \tau; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial T(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ & + \sum_p \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} N^p(t - \tau; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_p(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} J_{ijkl}(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial \Sigma_{kl}(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \\ & + \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} \alpha_{ij}(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial T(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \\ & - \sum_p \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} \gamma_{ij}^p(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial \xi_p(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \\ & + \frac{1}{2T_0} \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} C(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial T(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial T(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \\ & + \sum_p \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} \kappa^p(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_p(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial T(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \sum_q \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{D}} B^{pq}(t - \tau, t - \lambda; \mathbf{D}) \frac{\partial \xi_p(\tau, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial \xi_q(\lambda, \mathbf{X})}{\partial \lambda} d\tau d\lambda \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

MICROMECHANICS AND HOMOGENIZATION FOR FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER-MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH OXIDATION AND DAMAGE

Based on experimental observations, thermal oxidation of a carbon/polyimide composite is primarily a surface reaction phenomenon in a thin layer. For axial oxidation of a fiber composite with the oxidation zone developing along the fiber-matrix interface, the reaction moves along the interface in a self-similar manner [2]. Micromechanics modeling of the problem warrants a 3-D unit cell be chosen as the representative volume element to approximate the transversely isotropic nature of the axial oxidation in the composite. Two-scale coordinate systems are used in the model with a moving coordinate system affixed to the moving front of the active oxidation zone shown in Fig.4.

Since the reaction advancement is linear in time as indicated in the experiments [2, 3], through a transformation in time domain, a steady-state computational scheme can be established in the micromechanics analysis. The well-known homogenization method [19] is used to model the microstructural details of the fiber composite. A computational micromechanics approach based on a 3-D finite element formulation is employed to determine thermal oxidation-induced stresses and deformations as well as global effective thermomechanical property degradation.

Fig.4 (a) Axial oxidation of fiber composite with hexagonal periodic microstructure in two-scale coordinate system; (b) 3-D representative volume element with the moving coordinate system affixed to the front of the active oxidation zone.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE: A CASE STUDY

A case study is presented on this section for thermal oxidation modeling of a G30-500/PMR-15 composite at $T_1 = 343^\circ\text{C} / 650^\circ\text{F}$. The stress-free reference state is taken at the post-curing temperature $T_0 = 316^\circ\text{C} / 600^\circ\text{F}$. Both the microscopic stresses induced by temperature and oxidation and the macroscopic property degradation for the damaged composite are determined.

(1) Constitutive Relations

The total strain in the composite subject to thermal oxidation can be written as a sum of initial, mechanical, thermal and oxidation reaction-induced strains:

$$E_{ij} = E_{ij}^I + E_{ij}^T + E_{ij}^{Ox} + E_{ij}^M \quad (10)$$

where

$$E_{ij}^T = \int_{T_0}^{T_1} \alpha_{ij}(T; \mathbf{D}) dT \quad (11)$$

$$E_{ij}^{Ox} = -\int_0^{\xi_1} \gamma_{ij}^{Ox}(\xi; \mathbf{D}) d\xi \quad (12)$$

$$E_{ij}^M = S_{ijkl}(T_1, \xi_1; \mathbf{D}) \Sigma_{kl} \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha_{ij}(T; \mathbf{D})$ are coefficients of thermal expansion; T_0 and T_1 , reference and current temperatures, respectively; $\gamma_{ij}^{Ox}(\xi; \mathbf{D})$, coefficients of oxidation reaction contraction; ξ_1 , current extent of oxidation reaction; and $S_{ijkl}(T_1, \xi_1; \mathbf{D})$, elastic compliance coefficients.

Carbon fibers are considered as thermally stable at this level of oxidation temperature. Since thermal oxidation of the polyimide resin results in volatile products, oxidation-induced strain is negative. In the present finite element analysis, the oxidation-induced strain in the matrix phase is taken as $E_{ij}^{Ox(m)} = -0.4\%$ ($i = j$) and $E_{ij}^{Ox(m)} = 0$ ($i \neq j$) in the oxidized surface layer and decreases linearly in the active oxidation zone.

(2) Effective Thermomechanical Properties and Oxidation-induced Damage

The periodical solutions are first solved at the micro-scale by 3-D finite element analysis. Local stress and strain fields are obtained and then used to establish effective constitutive relations. The effective stress and strain in the oxidizing fiber composite are calculated by taking volumetric averaging of the local stress and strain in the region with oxidation reaction:

$$\bar{\Sigma} = \frac{1}{V_{\Omega} v_{\Omega}} \int \Sigma dV \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{1}{V_{\Omega} v_{\Omega}} \int \mathbf{E} dV \quad (15)$$

The effective elastic compliance tensor is determined by

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}} = V^{(f)} \langle \mathbf{S}^{(f)} : \mathbf{A}^{(f)} \rangle + (1 - V^{(f)}) \langle \mathbf{S}^{(m)} : \mathbf{A}^{(m)} \rangle \quad (16)$$

where $V^{(f)}$ is the fiber volume fraction; $\mathbf{S}^{(f)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(m)}$, compliance tensors of the fibers and the matrix; $\mathbf{A}^{(f)}$ and $\mathbf{A}^{(m)}$, stress concentration factor tensors for the fiber and matrix phases in the oxidation-induced damaged composite; and $\langle \dots \rangle$ represents the volume average of individual constituent phases.

The oxidation-induced damages may be determined by the current and initial effective modulus:

$$D_T = 1 - \bar{E}_T / \bar{E}_T^0, \quad D_L = 1 - \bar{E}_L / \bar{E}_L^0 \quad (17)$$

where \bar{E}_T and \bar{E}_L are current effective transverse and longitudinal Young's modulus, and \bar{E}_T^0 and \bar{E}_L^0 are initial effective transverse and longitudinal Young's modulus.

The effective transverse and longitudinal thermal expansion coefficients of the oxidation-induced damaged composite are obtained as

$$\bar{\alpha}_T = \bar{E}_T^T / \Delta T, \quad \bar{\alpha}_L = \bar{E}_L^T / \Delta T \quad (18)$$

where \bar{E}_{ii}^T are effective thermal strains of the damaged composite due to temperature change ΔT .

(3) Microstructural Geometric Parameters

Geometric parameters for the 3-D micromechanical modeling are shown in Table 1. The fiber volume fraction $V^{(f)}$ is 0.65 and fiber diameter ϕ , 7 μm . The total length of the unit cell used in the numerical simulation is chosen to be much longer than that of the region with oxidation reaction.

Table 1. Geometric parameters for 3D micromechanical modeling

x_0/ϕ	d_L/ϕ	d_1/ϕ	d_0/ϕ
0.59	20.00	1.00	1.00

(4) Thermomechanical Properties of Constituent Phases

Thermoelastic properties of carbon fibers and the neat polyimide resin are given in Tables 2 and 3 [20]. Carbon fibers are assumed to be transversely isotropic, and the neat polyimide resin is isotropic, with the carbon fibers having a positive transverse thermal expansion coefficient, but a negative longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient.

Table 2. Thermoelastic properties for carbon fibers

	E_{11} (Msi)	E_{22} (Msi)	G_{12} (Msi)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	α_{11} ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)	α_{22} ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)
G30-500	33.8	3.35	1.30	0.20	0.40	-0.30	5.60

Table 3. Thermoelastic properties for the neat polyimide resin at $T=343^\circ\text{C}/650^\circ\text{F}$

	E (Msi)	ν	α ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)
PMR-15	0.24	0.35	20

(5) Numerical Discretization

3-D finite element meshes are generated with 20-node isoparametric solid elements, using PATRAN for the two cases, one with perfectly bonded fiber-matrix interface and the other with partially debonded interface. Totally 3840 elements and 17341 nodes are used for the perfectly bonded case, and 18101 nodes with the same number of elements for the partially debonded case.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1) Thermal Oxidation-Induced Deformations

Configurations for a G30-500/PMR-15 composite subject to thermal oxidation at 650°F/343°C are obtained first and shown in Figs.5 and 6 for the aforementioned perfectly bonded and partially debonded cases, respectively. For the partially debonded case, surface contact between the fiber phase and the matrix phase is assumed to be frictionless in the 3-D solid element model.

Fig.5 Thermal oxidation-induced deformation of G30-500/PMR-15 composite with perfectly bonded interface subject to thermal oxidation at 650°F/343°C.

Fig.6 Thermal oxidation-induced deformation of G30-500/PMR-15 composite with partially debonded interface subject to thermal oxidation at 650°F/343°C.

(2) Thermal Oxidation-Induced Stresses

Due to the mismatch in coefficients of thermal expansion for carbon fibers and the polyimide matrix, thermal residual stresses at the microscale are expected at this temperature in the composite. Due to the mismatch in coefficients of reaction contraction for carbon fibers and the polyimide matrix as well as the formation of the non-uniform skin-core structure, the oxidation reaction introduces additional residual stresses in the composite subject to thermal oxidation. The resulting thermal oxidative (radial) stress distributions are shown in Figs.7 and 8 for the G30-500/PMR-15 composite with perfectly bonded interface and partially debonded interface at 343°C/650°F in air. Comparison with the pure thermal (radial) stress distribution is also made for the case of perfectly bonded interface at the same temperature without oxidation (Fig.9).

Fig.7 Thermal oxidative (radial) stress distribution in G30-500/PMR-15 composite with perfectly bonded interface subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure in air.

Fig.8 Thermal oxidative (radial) stress distribution in G30-500/PMR-15 composite with partially debonded interface subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure in air.

Fig.9 Pure thermal (radial) stress distribution in G30-500/PMR-15 composite with perfectly bonded interface subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure without oxidation.

In the G30-500/PMR-15 composite with perfectly bonded fiber-matrix interface heated in an inert environment, thermal deformation of the polymer matrix is positive and substantially overwhelms that of the carbon fibers. However, at the same high temperature in air, thermal oxidation of the polymer matrix and along the fiber-matrix interface causes reaction contraction which introduces high local dilatational microscopic stresses as shown in the results, thus providing a driving force for matrix microcracking and interface debonding. Also, the thermal oxidation itself may lead to environmental degradation of the polymer matrix and the interface. The oxidation-induced surface microcracks and fiber-matrix interface debonding, in turn, provide new surface areas for reaction, further advancing thermal oxidation penetration. This is consistent with the experimental observations as reported in [2-3, 5-9].

(3) Comparison of Pure Thermal and Thermal Oxidative Stresses

To illustrate quantitatively the effects of oxidation reaction on microscopic stresses, a comparison is made on the pure thermal stresses and the thermal oxidative stresses in the G30-500/PMR-15 composite (with perfectly bonded interface) subject to high-temperature exposure. In Fig. 10, distributions of σ_{rr} are shown for the two cases along the radial directions at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 30° . Also, angular distributions of pure thermal and thermal oxidative stresses are given in Fig.11 along the fiber-matrix interface. The magnitudes of the maximum pure thermal and thermal oxidative interface stresses are given in Table 4 for comparison.

Fig.10. Comparison of pure thermal and thermal oxidative stresses in G30-500/PMR-15 composite (with perfectly bonded interface) subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure.

Fig.11. Comparison of pure thermal and thermal oxidative interface stresses in G30-500/PMR-15 composite (with perfectly bonded interface) subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure.

The thermal oxidative stress level is found to be much higher than the pure thermal stress level. More importantly, the oxidation reaction-induced stress field is dilatational in nature. The maximum oxidation-induced stress in the matrix is found at the fiber-matrix interface with the longest distance

between the adjacent fibers ($\theta = 30^\circ$). The maximum oxidation-induced shear $|\sigma_{rz}|$ is located at the same position ($\theta = 30^\circ$). The oxidation-induced tensile interface stress σ_{rr} seems to be the dominant one controlling interface debonding during thermal oxidation since it is the highest among all thermal oxidative stress components in the composite and its strength is generally the weakest.

Table 4. Maximum interface stresses in G30-500/PMR-15 composite subject to high-temperature (343°C/650°F) exposure for pure thermal and thermal oxidation cases.

Case	Interface stress σ_{rr} (ksi)	$ \sigma_{r\theta} $ (ksi)	$ \sigma_{rz} $ (ksi)
Pure thermal	-0.02	0.08	0.26
Thermal oxidation	4.53	0.22	1.90

(4) Oxidation-Induced Damage and Associated Property Degradation

Effective thermoelastic property degradation for the oxidation-induced damaged G30-500/PMR-15 composite at T=343°C/650°F is also determined by the homogenization method and given in Table 5. The superscript “0” associated with the properties stands for the virgin state. The subscript “L” denotes composite longitudinal properties and the subscript “T”, transverse properties. Thermoelastic property degradation occurs as a result of thermal oxidation-induced microstructural changes. The damage variables are determined numerically from Eq. (17) and found to have the values $D_L = 0.01$ and $D_T = 0.52$. The effective transverse Young’s modulus is found to decrease most severely due to the fiber-matrix interface debonding, while the effective longitudinal Young’s modulus changes little. Interestingly, the effective longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient $\bar{\alpha}_L$ is seen to increase significantly due to interface damage whereas the effective transverse thermal expansion coefficient $\bar{\alpha}_T$ changes a little.

Table 5. Effective thermoelastic property degradation for oxidation-induced damaged G30-500/PMR-15 composite at T=343°C/ 650°F

\bar{E}_L^0 (Msi)	\bar{E}_L (Msi)	\bar{E}_T^0 (Msi)	\bar{E}_T (Msi)
22.06	21.81	0.89	0.43
$\bar{\alpha}_L^0$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)	$\bar{\alpha}_L$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)	$\bar{\alpha}_T^0$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)	$\bar{\alpha}_T$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{F}$)
-0.16	7.29	11.97	10.22

CONCLUSIONS

Modeling of high-temperature behavior of fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites has been attempted by a thermodynamic theory with reactions and damage. A 3-D micromechanical study is introduced to account for coupled oxidation reaction and microstructural change in the composite. A computational micromechanics approach based on the homogenization theory and finite element method is used in conjunction with the high-temperature experiments. Interactions among thermal oxidation, oxidation-induced damage and the fiber-matrix interface are determined. Thermomechanical property degradation associated with the oxidation-induced damage is also determined analytically. The microscopic stresses and deformations caused by thermal oxidation in the composite, especially along the fiber-matrix interface, are explicitly calculated. High microscopic stress concentrations in tension are found to occur in the oxidizing composite. Their effects on microstructural damage in the form of matrix microcracks and fiber-matrix interface debonding may be assessed, resulting from oxidation reaction itself as well as the induced thermal oxidative stresses.

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